

The Role of Brand Image in Mediating the Influence of Innovation and Price Perception on Purchase Decisions for Idemu Products in the West Jakarta Sales Area

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Abstract:- The research was conducted to analyze whether brand image has a simultaneous or partial influence as an intervening variable in the influence of innovation and price perception on consumer purchasing decisions for Idemu products with sales area restrictions in West Jakarta. The research applies quantitative methods and probability sampling. Researchers distributed questionnaires to 190 respondents who were customers who had previously purchased Idemu products. Data was collected and processed using the PLS method using SmartPLS software. The research results show that brand image has a partial influence as an intervening variable from the price perception variable on the purchasing decision variable, meanwhile brand image does not have a mediating influence from the innovation variable on the purchasing decision variable. The price perception variable has a significant influence on the brand image variable, but not so on the innovation variable. The innovation variable and price perception each have a significant influence on the purchasing decision variable. The impact of the results of this research can be applied to companies to create policies in terms of strategies focused on developing brand image to achieve company goals, that's achieving sales targets.

Keywords:- Brand Image, Innovation, Price Perception, Purchase Decision.

I. INTRODUCTION

The furniture industry has developed rapidly. In this century, the furniture industry has entered the industrial era 4.0. Industry 4.0 has an integrated digital system, namely a smart factory system that can be applied to the furniture industry. Smart factory systems can integrate production and consumer data to create custom furniture that suits consumer wants and needs.

Vivere group, which is a large corporation in the furniture sector, has launched a new business unit in 2019 with the Idemu brand. Carrying the concept of maximizing space, Idemu is present as the first custom furniture brand in Indonesia with a manufacturing system and own factory as well as 4.0 design technology.

Idemu's sales graph for a total of 2 years experienced a decrease and increase in sales figures due to several factors, including the influence of brand image which had an impact on consumers' decisions to buy goods. Apart from that, the need for furniture in residences is also influenced by consumer behavior in terms of ways of working changing from previously working from the office to working from home. And also the influence of competitive product prices compared to their quality.

Idemu's Instagram social media account provides other influences to strengthen the brand image, including consumer testimonials, especially celebrity endorsements and the blue check mark which indicates a verified account. Brand image comes as a result of using social media as a promotional and branding medium. So the final impact is in increasing sales results for Idemu.

Another aspect of social media marketing that supports increased sales is the blue tick verified account factor. In this phenomenon, on the Idemu Instagram account there is a blue tick and the number of followers is 125,000 accounts (2022 update in July). One of the contents on the Idemu Instagram account contains a celebrity's testimonial about Idemu products used in their home.

The content on the Idemu Instagram account contains consumer testimonials which can shape public perception about the product, the use and benefits of the product after use and the service of Idemu staff to consumers. The content from the Idemu Instagram account contains a testimonial from one of Idemu's consumers. This fulfills aspects of factors that influence brand image, so that the content can shape the perceptions of potential consumers.

The influence of the Covid pandemic has caused consumer behavior to change from work from office to work from home, so that a set of equipment to support work or complete home needs is needed. In response to market needs, Idemu offers innovative multifunctional furniture designs. One of them is the Tatami and Murphy Bed design. This design is one of the design innovation variants that is most popular with consumers because it can be a solution to usage needs in limited areas.

The tatami and murphy bed designs are present as innovations to answer the needs of narrow areas but still require various functions. So it can be a factor in consumer purchasing decisions. Innovation in Idemu products is also present in terms of materials. The material used is MFC (Melamine Face Chipboard) with international environmental friendly standards, so the product is more environmentally friendly and the quality is guaranteed.

Other brands operating in the same field use different materials, resulting in different product quality and ultimately different product prices. So the innovation of your product idea (in this case the design and material quality) will be a factor that determines the selling price of the product. Price is a very important factor in selling a product. The superior quality of the materials and product design of your idea will set a high price. Prices are based on final design results, specifications and ongoing promotions. Price shapes consumer perceptions of a brand, assessed by the reciprocity of the product obtained with the costs incurred.

Comparison of the prices of Idemu products with competing competitors makes consumers choose Idemu products by considering the benefits obtained such as guarantees, quality and branding.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Marketing Management

Marketing and management become a function, namely marketing management. Marketing management is the activity of carrying out managerial functions in the marketing process. So that an organization's marketing goals are achieved efficiently and effectively.

B. Consumer Behaviour

Consumer behavior is the behavior shown by consumers in choosing and deciding on several alternative products and services to purchase and own. Consumer behavior includes consumer decisions regarding what to buy, whether to buy or not, when to buy, where to buy and how to buy.

C. Purchase Decision

A purchasing decision is defined as a choice from two or more alternative options. And the availability of more than one alternative choice is a necessity in the decision making process.

D. Brand Image

Brand image can be defined as the perception of consumers' thoughts when remembering a brand. Brand image needs to be built through all media to convey a brand's message through symbols, media or visuals, atmosphere and events.

E. Innovation

Innovation is defined as an idea that is realized and accepted by a group of individuals for adoption. Product innovation is a process carried out by an organization or company in developing, improving and enhancing existing products.

F. Price Perception

perception is the consumer's view of the price paid and the benefits of the product purchased.

III. METHODOLOGY RESEARCH

A. Research Design

This research is causal research or research that aims to test hypotheses about the influence of one or several independent variables on other variables (dependent variables). In this research, the aim of causal research is to determine the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable and its mediating influence. Indicator measurement uses an ordinal Likert scale.

Fig 1 Framework

Variables X1 and X2 are independent variables, variable Y is an endogenous variable that functions as a mediator and variable Z is the dependent variable.

B. Population and Samples

The population used in this research are consumers who have purchased Idemu furniture products in the period Q4 2019 to Q1 2022. The total population is 652 consumers in the West Jakarta sales area.

The sample is categorized into probability because the population has been clearly collected and directed towards where the research data will be collected because it has been stated in the company database as secondary data. The sampling technique is simple random sampling.

In this study, the number of research indicators was 35, according to the Hair formula, a minimum sample size of $5 \times 35 = 175$ respondents was obtained.

C. Data Collection Methods

Data was collected using primary and secondary methods. In the primary method, the author collects data directly from respondents. The data collected is in the form of answers to questionnaires distributed. Questionnaires are distributed to samples that have been recorded in the database of consumers who have purchased. Questionnaires with a Likert measurement scale were distributed via online channels using the Google Form tool.

In the secondary method, data is obtained from internal company data. The data collected is in the form of sales reports, latest product lists and consumer databases.

D. Data Analysis Method

The next stage after the data has been collected is data analysis and processing. First, just to find the characteristics of the respondents, the data was processed using IBM SPSS Statistics to obtain descriptive analysis.

Next, data processing uses the PLS (Partial Least Square) method, which is a variant of SEM (Structural Equation Modeling). PLS analysis using SmartPLS software. This method was chosen because this research has a causality function and determinant objectives. As well as assessment through manifest or indicator variables and ordinal data scale measurements which fall into the parametric category so that they are more in line with the characteristics of the PLS method. Apart from that, PLS also supports causal tests between exogenous variables and endogenous variables, where in this research the endogenous variable whose influence is sought as a mediator is the brand image variable.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this chapter there will be a discussion of the research object, descriptive analysis, quantitative analysis, validity test results and reliability test results. The research object chosen was a furniture company with the Idemu brand. Descriptive analysis explains the characteristics of research respondents. Meanwhile, quantitative analysis explains the results of research model testing carried out using the SEM-PLS method using SmartPLS software. The final results of the research data will be linked to hypothesis testing to produce hypothesis test.

A. Descriptive Statistics and Analysis

In this sub-chapter, data is presented to describe and present information about respondents and research variables which are discussed in more detail in the sub-chapter description of respondents and description of variables.

➤ Respondent Description

This research was conducted by obtaining research data obtained from 190 respondents. The target respondents are Idemu brand consumers who have purchased products in the West Jakarta area. In this way, the respondents of this study are representative to be asked for opinions or information relating to purchasing decisions related to branding, innovation and product prices.

The data shows that respondents were dominated by men with a presentation of 57.9% compared to women with a presentation of 42.15%. This shows that male consumers influence the purchase of Idemu products.

Descriptive data based on age shows that respondents are dominated by private sector consumers aged 31-40 years, totaling 60 people with a percentage of 31.6%. This shows that consumers with an age range of 31-40 years influence the purchase of Idemu products.

Descriptive data based on work shows that respondents are dominated by consumers who work as private employees, totaling 86 people with a percentage of 45.3%. This shows that consumers with private sector jobs influence the purchase of Idemu products.

Descriptive data based on marital status shows that respondents are dominated by consumers with married status, totaling 155 people with a percentage of 81.6%. This shows that married consumers influence the purchase of Idemu products.

Descriptive data based on type of residence shows that respondents are dominated by consumers who own apartment type residences, totaling 102 people with a percentage of 53.7%. This shows that consumers with apartment housing types influence the purchase of Idemu products.

Descriptive data based on area of residence shows that respondents are dominated by consumers with a residence location in Grogol Petamburan totaling 56 people with a percentage of 29.5%. This shows that consumers who live in the Grogol Petamburan area influence the purchase of Idemu products.

➤ Variable Description

- The innovation variable has an average (mean) of 3.90. This value indicates that the innovation in Idemu products can be categorized as having the latest innovation. Has a value almost towards the highest classification, namely very recent. And the standard deviation value is 0.76, which indicates that the distribution of data in respondents' answers tends to have homogeneous values.
- The price perception variable has an average (mean) of 3.80. This value indicates that the price of Idemu products can be categorized as having a price perception that is in line with consumer expectations. And the standard deviation value is 0.79, which indicates that the distribution of data in respondents' answers tends to have homogeneous values.
- The brand image variable has an average (mean) of 3.72. This value indicates that Idemu products can be categorized as having a brand image that is known to consumers. And the standard deviation value is 0.85, which indicates that the distribution of data in respondents' answers tends to have homogeneous values.
- The purchase decision variable has an average (mean) of 3.68. This value indicates that Idemu consumers can be categorized as having good purchasing decisions. And the standard deviation value is 0.80, which indicates that the distribution of data in respondents' answers tends to have homogeneous values.

B. Data Analysis Result

In this sub-chapter the results of data analysis are presented to describe information regarding respondents' answers as well as interpretation and analysis of the results of data calculations. Data is processed using the PLS method with the SmartPLS application. Outer model testing was carried out to determine the relationship between latent

variables and their indicators and inner model testing to determine the relationship between latent variables.

➤ *Outer Model Testing Result*

There are three measurement criteria used, namely Convergent validity, Discriminant validity, and Reliability.

• *Convergent Validity Testing Result*

Table 1 Convergent Validity Testing Result

Variable	Item	Outer Loading Value	Limitation of Outer Loading Value	Result
Innovation (X1)	Item1	0,791	0,7	Valid
	Item2	0,838	0,7	Valid
	Item3	0,826	0,7	Valid
	Item4	0,807	0,7	Valid
	Item5	0,867	0,7	Valid
	Item6	0,854	0,7	Valid
	Item7	0,789	0,7	Valid
	Item8	0,856	0,7	Valid
	Item9	0,857	0,7	Valid
	Item10	0,853	0,7	Valid
	Item11	0,837	0,7	Valid
	Item12	0,850	0,7	Valid
Price Perception (X2)	Item1	0,870	0,7	Valid
	Item2	0,893	0,7	Valid
	Item3	0,909	0,7	Valid
	Item4	0,900	0,7	Valid
Brand image (Y)	Item1	0,851	0,7	Valid
	Item2	0,878	0,7	Valid
	Item3	0,888	0,7	Valid
	Item4	0,825	0,7	Valid
	Item5	0,831	0,7	Valid
	Item6	0,864	0,7	Valid
	Item7	0,871	0,7	Valid
	Item8	0,876	0,7	Valid
Purchase decision (Z)	Item1	0,828	0,7	Valid
	Item2	0,854	0,7	Valid
	Item3	0,884	0,7	Valid
	Item4	0,865	0,7	Valid
	Item5	0,841	0,7	Valid
	Item6	0,863	0,7	Valid
	Item7	0,876	0,7	Valid
	Item8	0,849	0,7	Valid
	Item9	0,873	0,7	Valid

From the table 1, it can be seen that all item factor loading values (outer loading) are above 0.7. So the correlation between the reflexive indicator and the latent variable is declared valid.

• *Discriminant Validity Testing Result*

Table 2 Results of AVE Root Value and Correlation Between Constructs

Variable	X1 (Innovation)	X2 (Price Perception)	Y (Brand Image)	Z (Purchase Decision)
X1 (Innovation)	0.836			
X2 (Price Perception)	0.284	0.893		
Y (Brand Image)	0.267	0.461	0.863	
Z (Purchase Decision)	0.321	0.456	0.528	0.859

From the output table 2, namely Discriminant validity Cross Loading, it can be seen that all indicators have a greater correlation coefficient with each variable itself compared to the correlation coefficient value of the indicator with other variables, so it can be concluded that each indicator in the block is a constituent variable or construct in that column.

• *Heterotrait-Monotrait Validity Testing Result*

Table 3 HTMT Testing Result

Variable	X1 (Innovation)	X2 (Price Perception)	Y (Brand Image)	Z (Purchase Decision)
X1 (Innovation)				
X2 (Price Perception)	0.298			
Y (Brand Image)	0.269	0.485		
Z (Purchase Decision)	0.323	0.485	0.545	

From the output of the table above, namely HTMT, it can be seen that all indicators have a correlation coefficient that is smaller than 0.85, so it can be concluded that the construct data is valid in this model.

• *Reliability Testing Result*

Table 4 Reliability Resting Result

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Reliability Limit Value	Result
Innovation (X1)	0,961	0,966	0,700	Reliable
Price Perception (X2)	0,916	0,923	0,700	Reliable
Brand image (Y)	0,966	0,967	0,700	Reliable
Purchase Decision (Z)	0,956	0,957	0,700	Reliable

The test results based on the table show that the composite reliability and Cronbach alpha results show satisfactory values, namely the value of each variable is above 0.70. This shows that the consistency and stability of the instruments used is high. So that all constructs or variables in this research have become suitable measuring tools, and all questions used to measure each construct have good reliability.

Table 5 AVE Value Testing Result

Variabel	AVE Value	AVE Limit Value	Result
Innovation (X1)	0,699	0,500	Valid
Price Perception (X2)	0,797	0,500	Valid
Brand image (Y)	0,745	0,500	Valid
Purchase Decision (Z)	0,739	0,500	Valid

The AVE criterion for a variable to be valid is that it must be above 0.50. It can be seen that all variables have an AVE value of more than 0.5, so that these variables have good construct validity. These 5 things mean good convergent validity, meaning that the latent variable can explain on average more than half of the variance of the indicators.

• *Variance Inflation Factor Multicollinearity Testing Result*

Table 6 VIF Testing Result

Collinearity Statistics (VIF)		Collinearity Statistics (VIF)	
Variable	VIF	Variable	VIF
X1.01	2.569	Y03	4.145
X1.02	3.081	Y04	3.165
X1.03	3.197	Y05	3.132
X1.04	2.732	Y06	3.914
X1.05	4.153	Y07	3.913
X1.06	3.589	Y08	3.696
X1.07	2.679	Y09	4.190
X1.08	3.663	Y10	3.996
X1.09	4.372	Y11	3.454
X1.10	4.275	Z01	2.811
X1.11	3.364	Z02	3.409
X1.12	3.455	Z03	4.598
X2.01	2.714	Z04	4.193
X2.02	2.911	Z05	3.249
X2.03	3.347	Z06	3.614
X2.04	2.973	Z07	4.001
Y01	3.176	Z08	3.308
Y02	3.930	Z09	3.562

Based on the test results in the table 6, the calculation of the variance inflation factor (VIF) value shows that in this test the VIF value is <10, so it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity between the independent variables in the regression model.

➤ *Inner Model Testing Result*

• *R Square Testing Result*

Table 4. 7 R Square Testing Result

Variable	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Brand image (Y)	0.233	0.225
Purchase Decision (Z)	0.357	0.347

Based on the table 7, R-square value of the Brand Image variable is 0.225. This R-square value means that the variability of the Brand image construct which can be explained by the variability of the Innovation and Price Perception constructs is 22.5%. R2 values of 0.67, 0.33, and 0.19 can be concluded that the model is strong, moderate, and weak. With this it can be said that the influence is weak. The R-square value of the Purchase decision variable is 0.347. This R-square value means that the variability of the Purchase Decision construct which can be explained by the variability of the Innovation, Price Perception and Brand Image constructs is 34.7%. R2 values of 0.67, 0.33, and 0.19 can be concluded that the model is strong, moderate, and weak. With this it can be said that the effect is moderate.

• *Q Square Testing Result*

Table 8 Q Square Testing Result

Variable	SSO	SSE	Q ²
Innovation (X1)	2280.000	2280.000	
Price Perception (X2)	760.000	760.000	
Brand image (Y)	2090.000	1736.471	0.169
Purchase Decision (Z)	1710.000	1267.879	0.259

The decision making criteria if $Q^2 > 0$ indicates that the model has predictive relevance and if the Q^2 value < 0 indicates that the model lacks predictive relevance. From the output above, it can be seen that the Q^2 values are 0.169 and 0.259. Because the value is more than 0, conclusion of the model has predictive relevance.

• *F Square Testing Result*

Table 9 F Square Testing Result

Variable	X1 (Innovation)	X2 (Price Perception)	Y (Brand Image)	Z (Purchase Decision)
X1 (Innovation)			0.026	0.032
X2 (Price Perception)			0.211	0.067
Y (Brand Image)				0.170
Z (Purchase Decision)				

Based on the table 9 it can be conclude that influenced of exogenous latent variables to endogenous latent variable separated into two result, that is weak and moderate effect. Variable innovation on brand image, innovation on purchase decision and price perception on purchase decision. There was the variable that classified into weak effect. However that also have variable classified into moderate result there are price perception on brand image and brand image on purchase decision.

C. *Direct Effect Hypothesis Test Analysis*

Table 10 Direct Effect Result

Hipotesis	Std Coef Value	T Statistic	P-value	Result
H1 Brand Image → Purch Decision	0,377	4,262	0,000	Significant Effect
H2 Innovation → Purch Decision	0,152	2,126	0,034	Significant Effect
H3 Price Percept → Purch Decision	0,239	2,672	0,008	Significant Effect
H4 Innovation → Brand Image	0,148	1,856	0,064	Not Significant Effect
H5 Price Percept → Brand Image	0,419	5,407	0,044	Significant Effect

Testing of the proposed hypothesis is carried out by looking at the path coefficients which show parameter coefficients and t statistical significance values. The significance of the estimated parameters can provide information about the relationship between research variables. The limit for rejecting and accepting the proposed hypothesis is using a probability of 0.05.

D. *Indirect Effect Hypothesis Test Analysis*

In this analysis, we will see the magnitude of the direct and indirect influence coefficients of the dependent variable on the independent variable. Next, a mediation effect test is carried out to find out whether the mediating or intervening variable mediates the influence of the independent variable on the dependent or not. The results of the mediation effect test can be seen in the Indirect Effect output, if the P value is less than 0.05 then the independent variable has an effect on the dependent variable through the mediation variable.

Table 11 Indirect Effect Result

Hipotesis		Std Coof Value	T Statistic	P-value	Result
H6	Innovation → Brand Image → Purch Decision	0,056	1,594	0,112	Not Mediating Effect
H7	Price Percept → Brand Image → Purch Decision	0,158	3,150	0,002	Mediating Effect

From the Total Effect output it is known that the effect of price perception to purchase decision is significant but not same result with innovation. Because of that the conclusion result of the indirect effect is partial mediating.

E. Discussion

➤ *The Influence of Brand Image on Purchase Decision (Hypothesis 1)*

The first hypothesis states "Brand image has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions". Thus, to improve purchase decisions which have an impact on company revenue, the factor that needs to be maintained and even improved is staff service to consumers. Consumers are very happy and helped by friendly staff service so that consumers can easily get what they need. Meanwhile, the factor that has a score that is significantly related to service is testimonials. Testimonials need to be increased, especially by celebrities or endorsers, so that the public knows more about branding, products and their quality.

➤ *The Influence of Innovation on Purchase Decisions (Hypothesis 2)*

The second hypothesis states "Innovation has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions". Thus, to improve purchase decisions which have an impact on company revenue, there are factors that are perfect, namely product ergonomics, consumers feel that the product they purchased is ergonomic and in accordance with the room size and standard size of use, so that the product can be used optimally in their daily work. The factors that need to be maintained and even improved are the neatness of product finishing and installation results. The results of neat installation and finishing will make consumers very happy with the product and the activities they carry out, such as cooking or watching TV, are felt comfortably, making it easier for consumers to carry out their activities. Meanwhile, the factor that has the lowest score compared to the others is the need to improve design forms that are more functional according to the consumer's room in order to increase the functional value of a room.

➤ *The Influence of Price Perceptions on Purchase Decisions (Hypothesis 3)*

The third hypothesis states "Price perception has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions". Thus, to improve purchase decisions which have an impact on company revenue, the factor that needs to be maintained and even improved is the promos offered to consumers. Consumers are very happy if they are given promotions on their shopping transactions. The promotions given can be in the form of gifts or discounts, so that consumers feel they are getting more benefits besides getting the product they

purchased. Meanwhile, the factor that has a score that is significantly related to service is price which is considered not compared to quality, which can be interpreted as a price that is relatively expensive when compared to other brands that have similar products. One way to reduce this price is by providing promotions so that they are linear with tables of research and analysis results on price variables.

➤ *Influence of Innovation on Brand Image (Hypothesis 4)*

The fourth hypothesis which states "Innovation has a positive and significant effect on brand image" is not proven and can be declared not accepted. Hypothesis results are not supported, this can occur due to 2 factors. The first is because there is not enough data and the second is because the sample is wrong. However, for this reason, a wrong sample should not be possible because the samples studied are consumers who have purchased the product so it can be declared that the sample is absolutely correct. So it can be concluded that the sample data is not large enough. This deficiency can be a note for future researchers in order to obtain maximum and significant results.

Apart from that, another analytical discussion is that if innovation is increased, it does not necessarily mean that brand image will improve. Therefore, each of these variables must increase their respective roles. The factors that need to be improved are testimonials, especially from celebrities or endorsers. Meanwhile, the factors that need to be improved are more functional forms of design according to the room.

The results of the description of the innovation variable show perfect results leading to a score of 4.0, while for the brand image variable the resulting score is 3.72. So strong innovation should be able to influence brand image, but the opposite is true in the results of this research. Innovation still has a very weak influence on brand image.

If analyzed from the variable description table, it is known that the following brand image indicators can be improved in performance:

- Digital advertising on social media with interesting content. Marketing collateral content must contain more information about the products and innovations owned by the brand. For example, USPs and the latest product innovations, so that consumers are educated about product updates.
- Celebrity and endorser testimonials. Re-maximize KOL or endorser media as a connector for WOM testimonials. It is necessary to make a script about USP and product innovation so that when shooting is not only about aesthetics so that the KOL audience as Idemu's target market can know the advantages of the product and its impact on strengthening the brand image.
- Positive comments and reviews on social media. It cannot be denied that negative comments can influence potential consumers to buy. Likewise on Idemu's Instagram or Google review page, there are still negative comments regarding the installation results. To minimize these negative comments, the function of the project manager must be maximized as the person responsible for the project from installation to completion, so that there are

minimal complaints and no additional negative comments on social media.

➤ *The Influence of Price Perception on Brand Image (Hypothesis 5)*

The fifth hypothesis states "Price perception has a positive and significant effect on brand image." Thus, to improve the brand image which has an impact on the brand's recognition by the public, the factor with the highest influence is the promo factor. Meanwhile, the highest influence is the staff service factor. What can be combined is that the staff serves consumers well and explains and offers the products and promotions given.

➤ *The Influence of Brand Image in Providing a Mediating Influence Between Innovation and Purchase Decisions (Hypothesis 6)*

The sixth hypothesis which states "Brand image has a positive and significant mediating influence between innovation and purchase decisions" is not proven and can be declared not accepted. Thus, brand image cannot have an indirect influence on innovation if it is increased on purchase decisions, which will not have an increased effect. Therefore, each of these variables must increase their respective roles. The analysis for this hypothesis has the same context as the discussion of the analysis for hypothesis 4, namely maximizing brand image indicators first, so that it can provide a good mediating influence on all variables.

➤ *The Influence of Brand Image in Providing a Mediating Influence Between Price Perception and Purchase Decision (Hypothesis 7)*

The seventh hypothesis states "Brand image has a positive and significant mediating influence between price and purchase decisions". In this way, brand image can have an indirect influence on increasing purchase decisions which are influenced by price. Things that can be improved are staff service to consumers and providing product explanations along with promotions which will increase consumers' purchase decisions at that time.

V. CONCLUSION

After research was carried out on latent variables using the PLS (Partial Least Square) data processing method on research variables (Innovation, price perception, brand image and purchase decision), several conclusions were obtained as follows:

- Brand image has a positive and significant effect on purchase decision.
- Innovation has a positive and significant effect on purchase decision.
- Price perception has a positive and significant effect on purchase decision.
- Innovation has no significant effect on brand image.
- Price perception has a positive and significant effect on brand image
- Brand image has no mediates innovation on purchase decision.
- Brand image has no mediates effect innovation on purchase decision.

- Brand image has positive and mediates effect innovation on purchase decision.
- Brand image has a partial mediates effect on this research

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Author suggest to add other variables because the analysis of the R Square test results is very small, even though it is above the minimum value. Researchers predict that there are many other variables that can be used as research variables to support all hypotheses to be significant. One of the suggested variables is social media marketing for future researchers. Because it is felt that one of the things that supports brand image at this time is the role of social media marketing.

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